

Sparse Deep Learning for Cell Type Classification in Breast Cancer Using Multiplex Imaging

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Abstract. Imaging Mass Cytometry (IMC) is an important imaging technology for breast cancer research. However, there is still a lack of research on the development of efficient deep learning algorithms for classification of cell types based on IMC data. In this study, we propose a sparse deep learning approach and assess the importance of antibody markers that contribute to cell classification. The results of the experiment show that the key markers we identified align closely with those traditionally used for manual cell classification, which provide tremendous potential for future biological research.

Keywords: Breast Cancer · Cell type classification · Sparse Deep Learning

1 Introduction

Imaging Mass Cytometry is an advanced multiplexed imaging technology, and a critical task for its analysis is the classification of cell types [1]. Traditionally, cell classification relies on pre-selected antibody markers and manually defined intensity thresholds. This method, while allowing for certain specificity, is time-consuming, prone to subjectivity and inconsistency, limited by dataset size, and requires expert knowledge. Aiming to resolve this issue, we decided to train a cell classification model using deep neural network (DNN) given its efficiency and accuracy in classification tasks. Some studies have already made attempts in this direction [1]. In this study, we developed a sparse deep learning approach which not only empowers the cell population identification but also improves the model interpretability by identifying the importance of each marker through group regularization [2, 3].

2 Methods

2.1 Data Processing Methods

In this study, we have a data set of more than 40,000 cells obtained from 8 batches of IMC images, where the main challenges include inter-batch effects and data imbalance. We employed BBKNN (Batch Balanced K-Nearest Neighbors) approach to reduce batch effects and SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) to alleviate class imbalance.

Fig. 1. (a) An example of original IMC image displays the expression of five relevant antibody channels using different colours. The cell counts for the five cell populations of interest using manually defined markers. (b) This diagram illustrates a neural network utilizing Group L2 regularization for sparse learning and the red edge/neuron indicates the redundant weights/neurons identified by regularization. The Group L2 regularization can identify the essential features/neurons by evaluating all the outputs of a single neuron. (c) Visualization of the Ground truth and inference results. (d) The importance ranking of all markers. The left side uses all cell types as classification output and the right side is the example of binary classification experiment for the Fibroblast cells.

2.2 Sparse Deep Learning Method

As a classification problem, cross-entropy loss is used and Group L2 regularization is introduced as a penalty term for weight matrices. The introduced Group L2 regularization is used to select important features by identifying and shrinking the magnitude of redundant weight parameters. Specifically, by calculating the L2 norm for the group of weights of each input feature, the Group L2 regularization is defined as $\text{GroupL2Loss} = \lambda \sum_j \|\mathbf{W}_j\|_2$, where \mathbf{W}_j represents the weights of the j -th group and λ is the regularization parameter. Thus, the final loss function combines the cross-entropy loss and the Group L2 regularization: $\text{Loss} = \text{CrossEntropyLoss} + \text{GroupL2Loss}$. The mechanism of Group L2 regularization is shown in the Figure 1 (b).

3 Experiments

3.1 Data Setup

The ground truth data for DNN training is generated by the traditional wet-lab method, where thresholds for different markers are determined with reference to

previous single-cell sequencing data to classify specific cell types. These manually selected markers will be compared with the markers identified by the developed sparse deep learning approach. The data details are shown in Figure 1 (a).

3.2 Classification Results

The classification accuracy for each cell type is as follows: Myoepithelial 0.9534, Luminal Progenitor 0.7769, Luminal Mature 0.8720, Fibroblasts 0.9958, and Macrophages 0.8368. It can be observed that the classification accuracy is approximately proportional to the number of cells, indicating that increasing the data volume may further enhance the model’s performance. To further demonstrate the classification effectiveness, we performed inference on the test set. The visualization of the inference result is shown in Figure 1 (c).

3.3 Identification of Important Markers

The L2 norm of the group weight parameters is calculated for each marker. As shown in Figure 1 (d), the top-5 important markers match the manually selected markers precisely. With this interesting result, a binary classification experiment was set-up to learn the important markers for a specific cell type. Specifically, the target cell type is regarded as one class and the other cell types are regarded as another class. For example, Figure 1 (d) shows that the identified top 2 markers for fibroblast cells align with manual markers. Additionally, this importance ranking can be a useful tool for revealing the closeness of the biological relationship between a cell population and its surrounding neighbourhood.

4 Summary

In this study, we implemented a sparse deep learning method to identify the important antibody markers for cell type classification in IMC data. We compared our results with manual markers, finding a high degree of consistency. Our developed DNN model only include 6 layers and can be trained within 10 minutes on 4090. Overall, our results suggest the potential application of this model in identifying significant cell populations and beyond, even in cases where the expected markers are not well established.

References

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